

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING IN FORMING POLITICAL SOCIALIZATION IN THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUTH

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Annotation. The article analyzes the system of working with young people, the processes of their political socialization, the role of education and upbringing in these processes, in the republican and international context.

Keywords: Education, ideology, idea, political socialization, youth, national development, national values, Temur's regulations.

Today, the world is rapidly developing and changing. In the era of such socio-political, spiritual-enlightenment, economic changes, there was a need to create a clear conceptual doctrine that would embody all the features of the political socialization of young people, their worldview, intellect, way of thinking and mental potential.

Naturally, these problems were, first of all, the influence of the ideology of the totalitarian regime, which caused changes in philosophical thinking. According to the philosopher and scientist J. Tulenov, "A comprehensive knowledge of the laws of the origin and development of society, along with timely understanding and elimination of the contradictions occurring in its economic, political, spiritual spheres, plays a significant role in philosophical observation of the prospects for development"[1].

Totalitarian ideology, subordinated to political attitudes, has created unclear problems within the relevant spheres and is an obstacle to studying the basis of dialectical unity. Therefore, there was a need for an important and fundamental analysis of the historical formation of development, the reasons for which its complications, which have remained for centuries, have become an obstacle to the activation of education and upbringing in the system of work with youth. The first need was related to the change of consciousness and thinking. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, emphasized that "it is no secret to anyone that the new society we are building, the processes of renewal that are increasingly entering our lives, the fate and future of reforms depend primarily on the support of our people for these changes. Today, in this regard, the activity of our people in the regions, their worldview, and the rise of consciousness and thinking are a matter of great

importance. We must never forget this simple truth"[2]. The second need is to study the consequences of the ideology of the former Soviet Union, slavery of thought and dependence on thought from the perspective of democratization and liberalization of the country, and to intensify the ways to eliminate them as much as possible. The third need is to study the national characteristics of philosophical thinking in the formation of education and upbringing as a scientific problem and to determine the objective reasons and conditions. Since this is the case, it is an urgent issue to study the historical-heritage relationship with the present and the future, taking into account the needs for the development of education and upbringing.

From world experience, we can see that the development of national philosophy in each country is associated with the development and formation of the specific statehood of the people of that region. This, of course, requires strong statehood and the development of strong philosophical thinking in this country.

In the candidate's dissertation entitled "The Problem of Man in the Paradigm of Western Anthropocentrism" by the Russian philosopher T.G. Nikishina, anthropocentric thinking was presented in the anthropology of the Renaissance, within the framework of the classical paradigm, that is, it developed outside the framework of the classical interpretation. At the turn of the 20th-21st centuries, a new "postclassical paradigm" of anthropocentrism was formed, analyzing the problems of the development of the central factor of human consciousness within the framework of scientific and philosophical directions and identifying the features of thinking. The author argues that the paradigm of anthropocentrism exists through the essence of man, his thinking, and that this reflection is responsible for maintaining the harmony of the dialectical unity between culture and nature[3].

The renewal of the life of our people was formed on the basis of the ideas of national independence. Now, the relations emerging in the form of a national philosophy serving the interests of man make it urgent to evaluate the entire past with a new look, and to reconsider it, and on this basis to develop historical memory and thinking with new national ideas. In this regard, a person must correctly and objectively assess historical events, analyze the environment in which he lives, existing problems. The reforms taking place in Uzbekistan today require historicism, objectivity, as well as confidence in the future. Only people who have a strong historical mindset and can objectively assess events will be able to inspire confidence in the future and the current fundamental changes.

The significant changes that took place in our socio-political, spiritual-enlightenment, and economic life, in the consciousness, lifestyle, and mentality of citizens during the period of independence were truly of great importance. All this is not a reality taken from outside, but is the historical result and fruit of our nation's centuries-old dreams and aspirations, based on the historical and spiritual experience of our nation, and it is necessary to understand the identity that is being formed in the minds of our people and accept it as a component of this historical and legal phenomenon.[4]

Through understanding, knowing, and realizing identity, one can see the place and role of national philosophy in the development of society as a whole at the heart of new views. This is called "national development" without separating it from identity. The root of national development lies in knowing and understanding national identity. The question of whether this nation can take its place in the developed world depends on its creative activity, spiritual-cultural and socio-historical development, intellectual potential, heuristic research, life and activities being rationally managed based on the requirements of development.

Theoretical and practical activities related to the instillation of the essence of noble ideas that lead man and society to development into the hearts and minds of the entire population, especially the youth, and the formation of a new worldview and modern thinking are also of great importance. In this way, the social and philosophical thinking and philosophical views of our citizens have striven towards the idea of freedom. Such a shift has created a basis for citizens to realize their desires.

In today's social consciousness and philosophy, one of the most important problems in the democratic development of modern New Uzbekistan is, of course, the institutionalization, that is, the gradual development of education and upbringing. Theoretically, it is aimed at studying the phenomenon of education and upbringing, its interrelation with other forms of social life. The general result of such a study is aimed at comprehensively determining the nature of the object of study, explaining its national identity, and determining the specific goals of the ways of building education and upbringing in Uzbekistan. The phenomenon of education and upbringing is problematic from the epistemological situation itself. However, not only this problem, but also analyzing the essence of social life in our country, the sublimation of the social mechanism of development - the transition from a low level of the social system to a high level of efficiency.

The sublimation of development increases the efficiency of the construction of education and upbringing, creates changes in the thinking of society and the individual, acts as a mechanism of a cultural and historical process directed from the most difficult to the easiest, from the lowest to the highest, that is, towards spiritual ascension. The concept of sublimation is widely used in modern philosophy today. Through this, updated ideas are introduced into philosophical thinking, all positive and negative aspects related to human realization are revealed. This, in turn, makes it possible to determine the full analysis of the essence of the positive and negative aspects of our national philosophy. On this basis, the path to creating a modern holistic concept in the development of national philosophy in the process of building education and upbringing opens up. Also, in his dissertation “The Phenomenon of Sublimation: Experience of Philosophical and Anthropological Research” by Yu.Yu. Pershin, he emphasizes that the elevation of thinking through the revival of the concept of sublimation, in which the philosophical worldview is renewed, helps to separate all the positive qualities associated with the territorial features of the thinking style from its negative aspects and replace them with aspects that elevate thinking. In this regard, the development of education and upbringing creates an opportunity to conduct a complete analysis of the social and philosophical thinking of man. In his opinion, an attempt is made to create a modern holistic concept of man.[5]

In her dissertation “The Sublimation of Ethics by B.P. Vysheslavitseva,” the scholar A.V. Abramova emphasizes that at a time when society was paying increased attention to the moral education of young people in the late 20th and early 21st centuries, there was an urgent need for Russian culture to turn to the philosophical heritage of thinkers. She also notes that this period was characterized by social instability, weakening and fragmentation of moral recommendations, and in order to overcome such a crisis situation, it is necessary to use the sublimation of the philosophical and spiritual heritage as the most effective theoretical context for preventing contradictions in the culture of the whole nation and youth. The ideas put forward by the author justify the fact that in the development of education and upbringing, a spiritually elevated, morally mature mindset is determined by showing a way out of the morally unstable situation of the present time[6].

In order to direct the moral consciousness of the individual and the entire spiritual world to new needs arising from the development of social relations, the principle of sublimation, moral thinking to a higher level, and efforts are

being made to implement clearly defined target tasks of human thinking in education and upbringing. In the development of education and upbringing, as well as in the ideological direction of national philosophical thinking, our need to study our national heritage has further strengthened. These needs are assessed as an organizational and legal condition for the genesis and development of democratic thinking. The reason for this is that the conceptual youth education and upbringing that we are trying to create is to determine the place of national philosophical thinking between society and youth in order to develop democratic principles on the basis of leading theories. A correct assessment of the past is not only a theoretical task, but also an important and necessary issue for the transfer of social experience of past generations to solve today's practical tasks of society and the correct formation of people's value relations towards their history and culture[7].

Our people have a three-thousand-year history and have gone through several stages. During this period, changes have occurred in the development of thinking, which has been enriched and improved along with complex processes. However, regardless of the state and how historical events unfold, the national philosophical heritage always serves the maturation and development of society, especially the youth, "democracy, as emphasized in modern political theories, is not an ideology to be exported, it is a process that leads to appropriate goals only when each people or nation passes through an evolutionary path in its development[8].

In the development of education and upbringing, the national philosophy is to adapt the consciousness and thinking of young people to life in a new way and apply it rationally in the spiritual development of a person. They have a developed level of thinking, lead with their spiritual, intellectual potential, and ability to confront life's problems. We characterize modern thinkers, that is, people who are free from the vices of the recent past, such as complacency, dependence, careerism, bribery, and selfishness, who think about the fate of the country, the people, and its prospects, and who are real creators of the socio-political and economic level of the nation's development, as spiritually perfect people.

National philosophical thinking refers, first of all, to the process of consciously understanding and applying to society the values, traditions, and spiritual heritage that belong to a nation and have passed through its historical experience.

Any creative ideas that have been tested over the centuries are later reflected in human thinking, are nourished by the national idea, and become valuable property due to the development process of education and upbringing of society and youth. It is precisely in the formation of our national philosophical thinking that the importance of our spiritual heritage “Avesta”, which represents three thousand years of history, is incomparable. One of the important aspects inherited from Zoroastrianism to Eastern thinking is the awareness of identity, the perception of will and freedom, which in essence awakens the desire to develop education and upbringing. As we know, our national philosophical heritage “Avesta” testifies to the fact that our people moved from dispersion to living as a community, formed a state from several tribes, clarified territorial neighborhoods, territories, preserved the integrity of their state territory, and laid the foundation for a centralized state. In the Avesta, the main principle was the study of the role of the family in society, the foundations of its formation, and the issues of morality, etiquette, enlightenment, and culture.

Another characteristic feature of ancient Eastern philosophy is the primacy of the spirit, reflecting the interests of the community, over the individual opinions of individuals. Talented individuals are excellent representatives of this spirit and strive to rise to the stage of history[9].

Also, in Zoroastrianism, the main force that drives education and upbringing is thought, word, and practical experience, which are important qualities that manifest themselves. These aspects are the driving force of society and serve as experience in solving today's practical tasks for citizens.

Our centuries-old history and national philosophical heritage play a special role in developing education and upbringing at a high spiritual level and introducing citizens to a progressive society based on broad thinking.

In general, in Farabi's views, the individual and society are considered as two parts of the whole and cannot be studied separately. In his opinion, the essence and function of the government or state are determined primarily by its educational role. In Farabi's opinion, regardless of the method, it is necessary to provide more or less education to the population engaged in a certain type of labor or profession. The heads of state of the country are considered exemplary heads of families in education. The difference between this and family education is that state leaders use various methods to train members of society in their professions and try to raise people of different classes to the level of true humanity”[10].

Another great thinker of the East who made a great contribution to national philosophical thinking on the development of education and upbringing is Abu Ali Hasan ibn Ali Tusi-Nizamulmulk. His work “Politics” provides a detailed analysis of the role of citizens in building a just society. In this work, Nizamulmulk does not set out to give empty advice and instructions. Based on the experience of rulers of various states, generations, as well as his personal experience, he provides the necessary lessons and spiritual strength for the prosperity of society and its citizens. According to this thinker, “implementing a task without consultation is a sign of weakness of thought, such people are called egoists. The result of a task carried out without consultation and advice will not be good. Based on this, the decision-making process of each task should be decided with the wise and elderly, people who have seen the world”[11]. The great legacy of Nizamulmulk is of practical importance in improving education and upbringing.

It is permissible to observe the great potential, skills, knowledge and experience of our great grandfather Amir Temur in state administration and building a just civil society, and their significance in the present era. “Tuzuklar”, which serves as an invaluable guide in studying the philosophical heritage of Amir Temur, is a unique masterpiece of our scientific heritage.

These regulations were used as an important guide in managing state affairs. The great sage also gives the following instructions on the methods and techniques of governing the state, advising his children and grandchildren: Now my advice to my illustrious, happy children and talented grandchildren who conquer countries is that I have taken twelve things as my motto and achieved the position of a sultan. With the help of these twelve things, I conquered countries, ruled my kingdom, and adorned the throne of the sultan. Let them also follow these rules.[12] These reliable, good words and useful advice of Amir Temur are an important program in the development of education and upbringing and state governance. According to the great thinker and statesman Alisher Navoi, fair education and upbringing can be established by highly virtuous, spiritual people, who can put forward the ideas of building a virtuous society based on the improvement of spirituality. According to him, “People of Meaning” are people of high intellect. Their meaning is that people of this category are intelligent and strive to understand the essence and meaning of various relationships. Such people perceive their needs and interests in harmony with those of others, and consider it a pleasure to live in service to society and the people. They act with consideration for the consequences of

every action and reality, and deeply feel that this world is short and transient. "People of Meaning live striving to understand the world through the virtue of thinking bestowed on them by the Creator, to acquire knowledge and science on this path, and to become enlightened"[13]. Anyone who correctly understands and deeply feels this interpretation of Alisher Navoi understands well that spirituality serves as a powerful force that ensures the existence of humanity. This powerful force serves the development of virtuous and just education and upbringing of every individual, which leads to the unity of the nation, the harmony of the interests of social groups and different peoples in society.

In conclusion, today in our country the issue of society and its main foundation, the youth, their national philosophical thinking in the development of education and upbringing is of great importance. Studying the scientific heritage of our great thinkers and statesmen such as Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Nizam-ul-Mulk, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Amir Temur, Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, etc., the structure of the empire, the most basic principles of its internal and foreign policy management, the main problems facing our state, and the theoretical and practical issues of our national independence, based on their vast experiences, can be considered. In Farabi's words, "the ability to think, which is the nature of the mind, is the goal for the mind in action, the mind in action is the mind in action, that is, the mind in action" [14].

List Of Used Literature:

1. Туленов Ж. Ҳаёт фалсафаси. Т.: Ўзбекистон, 1993, Б.309.
2. Каримов И.А. Инсон манфаатларини таъминлаш, ижтимоий ҳимоя тизимини такомиллаштириш – устувор вазирамиздир. Ўзбекистон, Т.: 2007. 15 жилд. 98-бет
3. Никишина Т Г. Антропоцентризм Проблема человека в парадигме западного антропоцентризма Диссертация. М.: 2008, 142-стр.
4. Қўчқоров В. Маънавият-миллий ўзликни англаш.Т.: "Академия нашрети", 2008, Б.17.
5. Першин Юрий Юрьевич. Феномен сублимации: опыт философско-антропологического исследования. 2004, стр.-167
6. Абрамова Анастасия Владимировна Б.П.Вышеславцеванинг этика сублимацияси. НАШР ҚИЛИНГАН ЖОЙИ 2007, -138 с.
7. Бакиева Г.А. Социальная память и толерантность журнал 4/3
8. Хардт М., Негри А. Множество война и демократия в эпоху империи. Культурная революция, М.: 2006, -304 с.
9. Карим Тоҳир Миллий тафаккур тараққиётдан. Т.: "Чўлпон", 2003,Б.19.

10. Юлдашев Ф. Абу Наср Фаробийнинг “Фи маъоний ал-ақл” асарида гносеологик масалалар: монография. Т.: Тамаддун, 2012, Б.48.
11. Низомулмулк. Сиёсатнома ёки Сияр ул – мулк. Т.: Янги аср авлоди, 2008.Б.92-93.
12. Амир Темур. Тузуклар. Ўзбек, инглиз, француз ва рус тилларида. Т.: Extremum – press, 2016.Б. 65.
13. Хаққулов И. “Камол эт касбким...” Т.: Чўлпон, 1990. Б.80 – 81.
14. Фаробий. Фозил одамлар шаҳри. Арабчадан А. Ирисов ва М. Маҳмудов таржимаси. Қўлёзма

